

**SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF THE CONCEPT OF
BIOAESTHETICS**

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Annotation: This article gives information about concept of bioesthetics and its importance today, the role of biomedical problems and their role in the formation of youth aesthetic education.

Key words: Bioesthetics, aesthetic care, beauty, bioethics, cosmetic surgery, emotion, reality.

At the beginning of the twenty first century, treatment of the face surgery was named beauty surgery. Bioesthetic is a part of aesthetic and it is based on symmetry laws as a beauty learning subject. The symmetry law is characterized by living and lifeless objects. The symmetry is the numbers, which means that Greek philosopher Pythagoras said that “the numbers rescues the world” are important for each era. Biopolitics, biomedicine, bioethics and bioesthetics are at the top of the pyramid, the truth, love, beauty, and practical benefits are at stake. It is important to emphasize that bioeducation is broad term. If we say that bioenlightenment, biopolitics, bioethics and bioaesthetics are united at the tip of the pyramid, truth, love, beauty and practical utility are united at that peak. Another thing to note is that bioenlightenment should be understood in a broad sense.¹

Unpleasant ecological situation, stress, and harmful habits have a negative effect on our appearance. Time-High Judge, over time, the level of hormones that support the body decreases. As a result, wrinkles appear on the face. Skin changes are evident from the age of 40-45. At the same time, it is possible to make the face plastic. Plastic Operations We have not had time to use this term in our everyday life. The term "plastic surgery" is used for the first time by Karla Ferdinand Grafe in his Rhinoplasty work. This work was published in 1818, where the scientist speaks of the benefits of plastic surgery. According to the scientist I.V.Botvinko (2006) "Aesthetic characterism is the concept of the existence of the existence - checking, proximity, harmony, merging in different forms and unity. This principle is inherent

¹¹ Mhmc.in/bio_Aesthetic.aspx. интернет материаллари асосида(таржима).

to bioesthetics and it is related to nature and the existence. "Many think that plastic surgery is only used by artists. Of course, it is natural for the celebrity to be attentive to the appearance of others and to try to reproduce by plastic surgery. I'm talking about how plastic surgery helps ordinary people and what diseases. Today, plastic surgery is underway in two directions. These are plastic reconstructive and aesthetic plastic surgery. Plastic reconstructive surgery is an operation performed to overcome post-burnout changes, congenital traumas, and injuries. Plastic aesthetic surgery - aesthetic plastic surgery is used to prevent the aging process from appearing in the human body, especially age-related changes in the age of the skin.

So when can plastic surgery help?

When there are congenital abnormalities in the human body, most of them can be treated surgically (although they are many). Surgical hair and ears underneath the truncated chest are applied to them by the skin. Lab faults, nasal obstruction, excess fingers, hanging lids, lack of congenital breasts and so on. as well as the thickness of the throat, the nose and the jaw cause the person to lose confidence in himself and hate him.

"For the survivors of accidents and accidents, the issue of survival for life and death lies first. But after surviving, he wants to get rid of the injury. At the same time plastic surgery comes to the rescue. Helps eliminate defects in life. Many adolescents complained of emotional distress during childhood."² In some cases, this process is moderate, and in some cases overflowing and overflowing. This can not be cured by cosmetic methods. Many people are ashamed of their appearance. At the same time, the problem of meeting a qualified plastic surgeon is easily resolved. Consider the posture or the postpartum situation. As a result of these factors, some women's attitudes can change dramatically. Man wants to look younger, regardless of age.

There is no wonder today. We also hear about cases of plastic surgery, which has changed dramatically, and sometimes gave rise to complications. Plastic is sometimes a side effect because it is a must-have process, not a magic wand that can instantly alter the appearance. Everything needs to be respected. This is true of plastic surgery. If the client applying to the clinic requires a completely non-specific, even harmful action, the specialist should conduct explanatory work. Occasionally, a psychologist needs support. Because most of the mummy's patients are related to their inner experiences.

The sense of longing for everlasting youth has attracted the attention of humanity for a long time. Today's day is being accomplished by advanced

^{2 2} Mhmc.in/bio_Aesthetic.aspx. интернет материаллари асосида(таржима).

technology, which offers plastic surgery. But do you know that the roots of plastics go back to ancient times? The Egyptian physicians are extremely cautious in the care of the skin, while the other monuments of the same period are mentioned in papyrus. Even before nasal fractures, the skin covered the skin with pre-sutured oil, putting cotton on the nose cells, and then performing the operation. Aulus Cornelius Tselzus, a Christian scientist who lived in the first century, said that "it is very important that the suture be cut in the treatment of defects in the face". Rhinoplasty (nasal form correction) is widely used in ancient China and ancient Greece. The most important plastic surgery in ancient Rome was the loss of waist and waistline. This meant that the warriors had escaped the battlefield or their slavery. Naturally, these characters are often asked to get rid of people. Foreigners also used the correctional system to get their place in the Roman society. In addition, correction of the body has also been performed. In the seventh century, Alexandros from Alexandria, Paulos Ayjinsky, performed many operations on breast cancer. This disease is called ginekomastia (female breast), and occasionally there are cases of breast cancer in males. These operations are still taking place today. Only now are widely used in his new methods - liposaccation (lipos - fat, suction - absorption). In the 10th century there were reports of "rabbit lips" correction in China during Tan and Sun empires.

The injection to the lab contains silicone and acrylic gels. These substances can sometimes cause severe changes in the body or the spread of various diseases.

Shalangulyak 's treatment is an autoplatic and is administered from the age of six years. In fact, hepatitis can be cured up to six months by simple cure. Because the ear pups are still soft in this period. If autism is used, the technique of autoplasty (auto-ear, plastics) is used. Otoplasty occurs due to fibrillation, congenital malformations, or divorce in ear-nose ear in the ears, the length of the ear, the innate absence of the ear organism, and some of the injuries. For each patient, the specific surgical procedure is selected.

“Though it was the result of modern medical research, three hundred years ago, the book Avesto cared for and paid special attention to the need for a healthy pregnant woman to be healthy. Almost all ethical and aesthetic thoughts in the book Avesto are also relevant today, that is, our ancestors were concerned about the genetic and reproductive health of 3000 years ago.”³ This doctrine emphasizes the need for a healthy generation, the birth of a generous generation, a waking-up of a healthy lifestyle, washing hands with the hands, working with honesty, cultivating, and breeding livestock. First of all, parents need to know that their children are motivated by intellectual and physical care. Hum hood is said to be free of organs,

³ Ҳамиджон Ҳомидий “Авестодан Шохномагача”.:2007.

especially when you wash hands with your hands. It is said that the pregnant woman needs to eat halal, and that she and her husband achieve their honest work. Halal labor was considered to be farming and cattle breeding. "It's a good, intelligent, agile, brave, brilliant, good-looking, good-looking, good-looking, good-looking, good nature, created in the Ahuramaz, to make the surrounding environment clean and tidy, to enjoy the landscapes and to enjoy aesthetic pleasure from it, to the sons and daughters who know different languages, who can look far away and protect the country from trouble, and praise the generations of pure generations, who can see bright life with bright eyes. "

Today, we can see people and youths who are on the wrong track. For example, no one can guarantee the birth of a pregnant mother who is pregnant. The birth of a child with various hereditary diseases caused by a close marriage, which is not harmful to a genetic transformation, to the gene pool of the nation! "It is noteworthy that Avesto's book, Ahriman Breathe, is probably the same as those that are said to be missing. They also have surgeries in medicine. Surgical work was a lot frustrating, and the patient was responsible for healing, and even during pregnancy women were able to get pregnant with surgery."⁴ "The Vendidad section also provides information on the work of the first physician Tiriti in the world.

Experts say that only two years you can see the results of your practice. Then you may fall back to your previous situation or even worse. Because it does not fill the vacuum cleaner immediately."⁵

The most harmful ingredients in cosmetics are mineral oils, which are petrochemical wastes. They form the skin and cause allergies. It also slows skin regeneration. Diseases such as arthritis, migraine, diabetes, and epilepsy may develop in the body. Paraffin is also a product of petrochemicals that is more mineral oils. Glycerin does not moisturize the skin, but it dries. Propylene glycol is an oil refining product, mainly used as a brake fluid and antifreeze in the machine. This is a very strong allergy that causes hyperkeratosis and acne, and when it is collected in the body, liver and kidney toxic poisoning occurs.

Sodium sulfate or lauryl sulfate. Though toxic from coconut is toxic. It has a negative effect on the heart, brain, kidneys, and liver. It causes hair loss and sagging, allergic dermatitis, conjunctivitis, and even cataract.

⁴ Ҳамиджон Ҳомидий "Авестодан Шохномагача":.2007.121-бет.

⁵ Ҳамиджон Ҳомидий "Авестодан Шохномагача":.2007.121-бет.

Parabens break down the enzymes of the skin and act as the xenophobes that accumulate in the body and destroy the hormonal balance. According to some reports, parabens stimulate the development of breast cancer.

The International Islamic Fiqh Academy under the aegis of the Islamic Conference in 2010 decides:

- cosmetic surgery is a surgical procedure that serves to revitalize its function due to the appearance or damage of a person by changing one of the parts of the visible body;

- adherence to general conditions and norms for cosmetic surgery: Surgery should be performed in a careful manner. For example, re-establishing the task, reforming the guilt, and re-creating the origin;

- Surgery should not overcome the hoped benefits. This should be done by qualified and trusted people;

- The physician or nursing surgeon is a professional and professional of that profession and this responsibility is in accordance with Resolution 142 of the Academy;

- Surgical procedure with the patient's consent;

- I am in a position to be able to see the potential risks of being physically aware and aware.

- There should be no other side effects that may be painful. It should not be opposed to the shar'i sources.

The Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) said: "He has cursed the one who shapes his body with the needle and the hairdresser, the haircutter and the connector, the one between the teeth for the beauty, and the one who changes what Allah has made" . It is narrated from Ibn 'Abbas (RAAH) that a woman with a haircut and a haircutter, a woman who painted the body with a needle, and a figure who paints her painless body, are cursed. The Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) forbade man to look like a woman and likewise to a man like him. There is no harm when it is necessary or compulsory.

“Shari'ah rules: 1. Cosmetic surgery is a necessity and it is permissible. In particular, it is necessary to: a) return the form of the body to God's status; Allah reveals in the Qur'an in the following verse: "We created the human being in a most beautiful form." (Surat at-Tin, 4). b) return to a known member of the body; c) Reformation of national minorities, such as damaged lips, ruptured noses, cats, fingers, or teeth, or their finger clinging to it in the same way material or moral damage; g) Accidental casualties, such as fire, to correct defects due to illness. For example, removing the skin from the skin and removing some parts of the breast or hair while hair cuts, such as in women, especially if it is a pancreatic operation or a

risk of getting it; d) Loss of it, in particular, causes it to become loose. 2. Cosmetic surgery is not necessary medical care, it is not permissible for one to follow the desires of the human being in order to accomplish his desires, following his own desires or imitating others. For example, to appear in a particular form, or to swindle, to change the face, to change the shape of the nose, to make lips larger or smaller, and to change the shape of the eye and expand it. Reducing weight by scientific means, if weight gains the disease. If there is no alternative to surgery, it is permissible to perform surgical procedures on the condition that it is safe to do so.”⁶
4. It is not permissible to lose the wrinkle through the surgical or syringe, provided that it is not safe from the harm. 5. The specialist physician must follow the Shari'ah rules in medical practice and advise those who are doing the job. Because it is said that "religion is a sermon".⁷

So, when using the surgical procedure, we have to pay attention to:

do not use surgical procedures if it is not important;

- Knowing that he / she can lose self-esteem and reproduce the gene pool of reproduction;
- Necessary surgical practice (in various adverse events, overcoming congenital malformations) (some of the shortcomings may not cause fear in people);
- when limiting person's movement;
- The surgeons who practice surgery should be aware of and practice the principles of surgical practice.

⁶ Шайх Муҳаммад Содик Муҳаммад Юсуф «Зикр аҳлидан сўранг» .Тошкент

⁷ Шайх Муҳаммад Содик Муҳаммад Юсуф «Зикр аҳлидан сўранг» .Тошкент